

Information Dissemination: Implications for Religious Conflicts in Nigeria and Sustainable Development Agenda

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Abstract

This paper examines the extent to which religious conflicts have affected sustainable development in Nigeria. Theoretical, conceptual and global trends of religious conflicts have been analysed with a view to bringing forward the justification for the study. In Nigeria, religious conflicts have been found to negatively affect election processes, governance, security, migration, education and economic development. The resultant effect is the negative strain on the human, social, economic and environmental pillars of sustainable development. This paper has proposed the intentional repackaging of timely, relevant, authoritative and accurate information to counter the negative effect of religious conflicts for sustainable development in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Religious conflicts, Information Dissemination, Sustainable Development, Nigeria*

Introduction

Nigeria is a multi-religious country comprising thirty-six states and a Federal Capital Territory, with 774 Local Government Areas (LGAs). About fifty per cent of the population practice Islam while the rest adhere to Christianity. (Afegbua,2010) The other minority religions in the country include Hinduism, Judaism, the Baha'i Faith, and Chrislam (a syncretic faith that contains elements of Christianity and Islam). Nigeria as a country covers a total area of 356,667 square miles. In 2021, the country had an estimated population of 213 million; it is the seventh-most populous country in the world bordered by the Republic of Benin on the west, Chad and Cameroon on the east, and by Niger in the north, and the Gulf of Guinea in the south. Nigeria is a country of rich ethnic diversity with about 400 ethnic groups. The three largest ethnic groups in Nigeria are the Hausa, Igbo and Yoruba. The other major tribes in the country include Edo, Ijaw, Kanuri, Ibibio, Annang, Epira, Nupe and Tiv. Also, there are minority groups of British, American, East Indian, Chinese, white Zimbabwean, Japanese, Greek, Syrian and Lebanese immigrants in Nigeria. As the second-largest economy in Africa, Nigeria is classified as an emerging market because of its rich reserves of natural resources, and well-developed financial, entertainment and communications sectors. (Igwe, 2010) The transportation sector and stock exchange of the country add to the finances. The Nigerian Stock Exchange is the second-largest in Africa. Petroleum is a major product which plays a significant role in the economy of the country; it is the twelfth-largest producer of petroleum in the world. Manufactured products like leather, textiles, t-shirts, plastics and processed food enhance the economy of the country. Agriculture is also important, employing almost sixty per cent of Nigerians. Cocoa, sugar cane, yams, maize, palm oil, groundnuts, coconuts, citrus fruits, pearl millet, and cassava are the major agricultural products. However, health care, education, and security in Nigeria are still under the world standard, and these pose a serious threat to the otherwise advancing country. The national Independence Day in Nigeria

is celebrated on 1st October yearly, to commemorate its independence from the United Kingdom in 1960 and declared a Republic on October 1, 1963.

Conversely, in Nigeria, people have been disenfranchised by their own circumstances on the one hand, and their leaders' perfidy on the other. Conflicts arise when people compete for the same resources (such as territory, jobs and income, housing), natural resources (cultivable land, freshwater), poor governance, desire for independence, and clash of religious and political ideologies. Many leaders have weaponized religious and political differences as a tactic for keeping or gaining power. In the same way ethnic differences can cause conflict, or be made to cause it. Again, people's ethnicity gives them a sense of identity and belonging, and it is threats to this sense which can cause violent responses, just as individuals may lash out with angry words or gestures when they feel threatened. Indeed, conflicts of all kinds most frequently arise when people feel threatened - regardless of whether the threat is real. This paper analyses the effect of religious conflicts in Nigeria and the implications on information dissemination and sustainable development.

Methodology

The study is a qualitative analysis of secondary sources and personal observation of the researcher. A checklist of indicators for the variables was developed to guide the analysis. A data inventory was drawn for the period 1960-2023. The scope of the research is the entire population of Nigeria from independence in 1960 to 2023 and limited to only two religions- Christianity and Islam.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework on Religious Conflicts

Theoretically, a number of hypotheses connect religious factors or variables to conflict: First, from a socio-psychological point of view, diverse religious identities, similar to ethnic and other social identities, form a group identity and can result in escalating inter-group dynamics. As a result, violent escalation becomes likely. Second, religious identities are special. They are connected to particular religious ideas. Such religious ideas are shared values and norms legitimized by a transcendental source, and therefore it might be argued that they are hardly subject to negotiation and compromise given their accepted supernatural origin. This can also entail a higher propensity for violent behaviour by religious actors: religious extremists may demand that non-believers and adherents to different religious traditions have to be converted by force, and heretics may have to be punished. Conflicts over the role of religion in society or the state are likely to emerge between different religious groups, especially if the religion in question claims universal validity. Furthermore, combatants might be motivated through specific religious rewards for participation in acts of violence. Third, religion, or more precisely, religious factors might be understood as a possible mobilization resource for and in conflicts. This idea is by no means incompatible with the former two ideas, but this theoretical branch stresses the role of leaders in the

organization of collective action. In order to mobilize followers, leaders can choose from different identities, such as religious, ethnic, or other social identities.

Religious conflict has been studied by scholars for many years. Jonathan Fox (2002) In: *Ethno-Religious Conflict in the Late Twentieth Century: A General Theory* analyses different scholar- (Kowalewski and Greil, 1990; Lewy, 1994; Huntington (1993 & 1996; Hoffman 1995; Kennedy, 1999; Martin, 1989; Ranstorp, 19996; Rappoport, 1988 and 1999). There are several types of theories on religious conflict.

1. The first type of theory usually looks at the nature of the religions and the ideologies around them. These types of theories argue that certain types of religions are more likely to cause conflicts than others.
2. The second types of theories focus on the political, social and economic environment in which the religious conflicts occur. An example of such a theory is Huntington's Clash of Civilizations theory.
3. The third type of theories on religious conflict takes a structural approach to the relationship between religion and conflict. Kowalewski and Greil (1990) are of the opinion that the structure of the relationship between religious and political elites determine the church's involvement in conflict.
4. The fourth type is the 'laundry list' approach. This approach lists a number of ways in which "religion affects conflict but does not put them into a coherent conceptual framework."

Lewy (1974) uses the laundry list approach and lists a number of ways in which religion can be used politically to start or maintain conflict:

1. Revolutionary messianism, the struggle for an earthly paradise, can result in revolts when there is social or political distress or disorientation without a clearly perceived cause.
2. Militant religious nationalism materializes in situations of awakening national consciousness, where religion supplies a sense of national identity.
3. The leaders of religious bodies with a developed ecclesiastical organisation support a revolutionary upheaval because they are sympathetic to the aims of this revolution or because they are protecting the interests of the religious institution.
4. Religion can be manipulated for political purposes.

It should be noted that these manifestations of religious support are not mutually exclusive. To be truly dynamic, however, the laundry list approaches would also have to consider the general body of theory on conflict.

Religious Conflicts in Nigeria

Religious conflict is a term that has been variously defined by scholars. These definitions are diverse and they all convey the single meaning of disagreement between the two or more religious groups. Hornby (2006) defines religious conflict as a situation in which religious adherents are involved in a serious disagreement or argument with one religious group and another. This is a situation in which there are opposition in ideas, opinions, feelings and wishes. Olite and Olawale (1999) sees religious conflict as struggle over values and claims to scarce resources, status and power in which the aims of the opponents are to naturalize, injure, or eliminate their rivals. This definition very much suits, or reflects the conflict between Muslims and Christians in Nigeria. Gyuse (2006) further points out that when two more persons, groups, communities or nations seek to take possession or dominate a particular object of value at the exclusion of others, conflict ensues. Nnoli (2003) asserts that the concept of religious conflict contradicts the peace process arising from perceptions, behaviours, phenomena and tendencies.

Miall (1992) also posits that the emergence of religious conflict can be a situation where a where a clear contradiction exists or perceived to exist between the participants who view the outcome of such conflicts as extremely important. It would seem that Miall is stating the fact that suspicion fuels the religious conflict. Gotan (2004) cited a traditional definition of religious conflict as the conceive interactions in which two or more religious adherents engage in mutually opposing action and use coercive behaviour to destroy, injure, thwart or otherwise control their opponents. Aliyu (2004) sees religious conflict as “a process of social interaction involving a struggle over claim is resources, power and status beliefs and other preferences and desire”. For Oyeshola (2006) religious conflict is the disagreement, dispute or controversy in ideas or viewpoints held by two or more individuals, communities or religious groups. A religious conflict becomes violent if physical or emotional force is used to hurt or kill people (Sa'id, 2004). Gotan (2004) inferred that conflict is found everywhere in human interaction and it can occur in the family or the home, place of work, between different ethnic as well as religious groups as it is in the case of Muslims and Christians in Nigeria. Ayandele (1996) also postulates that religious conflict is a universal phenomenon and it becomes problematic, open, confrontation and violent if appropriate measures are not taken to curtail it. For the purpose of this study, the operational definition of religious conflict is the clash, contention, confrontation, battle, rivalry, controversy or quarrel among religious groups.

Global Trends in Religious Conflicts

In recent decades, religion has had considerable impact upon politics in many regions of the world. The belief that societies would invariably secularize as they modernize has not been well founded. Technological development and other aspects of modernization have left many people with a feeling of loss rather than achievement. By undermining “traditional” value systems and allocating opportunities in highly unequal ways within and among nations, modernization can produce a deep

sense of alienation and stimulate a search for an identity that will give life some purpose and meaning. In addition, the rise of a global consumerist culture can lead to an awareness of relative deprivation that people believe they can deal with more effectively if they present their claims as a group. One result of these developments has been a wave of popular religiosity, which has had far-reaching implications for social integration, political stability and international security. Examples of cases include experiences of Sikhs in Hindu India, the struggles of the peoples of Southern Sudan against Arabization and Islamization, Tibetan Buddhist opposition to the Chinese state and the African-American movement of self-development, the Nation of Islam. Syncretistic religious movements are said to be found predominantly among certain rural dwellers in parts of the Third World, especially in Africa. They involve a fusion or blending of religions and feature a number of elements found in more traditional forms of religious association, such as, ancestor worship and healing practices.

Community-oriented movements often emerge from attempts to improve community livelihood; these tend to be popularly driven and may have either conservative or reformist orientation, and are found typically, but not exclusively, in Latin America. Especially prominent in this regard are local community groups, mostly Roman Catholic in inspiration, which have grown in importance over the last 25 years in Latin America, the Philippines and in parts of Africa. Many derive their ideas from the tenets of radical liberation theology. In addition, there has been a strong growth in several Latin American and African countries of popular Protestant evangelical churches. What all these groups have in common is that local self-help groups are formed to improve qualitative communities' lives at a time when central and local governments are unable to satisfy popular developmental needs.

Religious Conflicts and Governance in Nigeria

Good governance will in effect mean the use of power by the government i.e. the President, and his ministers, senators, members of House of Representatives and how the public service operates: To promote democracy, accountability and transparency; to formulate and implement good policies ;to effectively and efficiently manage the Nigerian human and financial resources in order to achieve sustainable national development, to achieve economic prosperity to alleviate poverty (Yahaya 1999). Good governance becomes very fundamental and imperative when viewed against the backdrop of massive deterioration of government institutions, pervasive poverty and widespread unemployment, corruption, as well as the near total collapse of moral and ethical standards engendered by incessant religious conflicts and otherwise. Although conflict in Nigeria predates the inception of civil rule in 1999, the frequency of conflicts in all the geo-political zones at one time or the other in the present democratic dispensation calls for concern. Osita (2007) heaps the blame of Nigeria's religious and violent conflicts on corruption and greed for power. Hence the frequent conflicts in form of religious and ethnic in the country. The intense nature of competition for political power especially in the fourth republic has made violence to be associated with governance in Nigeria. Nigerian

politicians, over the years, have “become more desperate and daring in taking and retaining power and more intolerant of opposition, criticism and efforts at replacing them” (Alemika, 2011).

Religious Conflicts and Election Processes in Nigeria

In Nigeria, the interplay of religious conflicts and politics boils down to perceived or real loss of power by an elite stratum, the quest for political power among those who won it before, those that lost it and those who want it back. Nigerian politicians are known for playing ethnic cards for their selfish political gains. That is, inciting their own ethnic group against their opponent’s ethnic group. The violence that trailed the release of the 2011 presidential election in Nigeria, in the northern parts of the country, (the home of the major presidential candidate General Buhari (Rtd.) that lost out in the election) buttresses this fact. Added to the insecurity baggage is the Boko Haram insurgency in the north that has left not less than 16,000 policemen, soldiers and civilians, including politicians’ dead (Ogbonaya et al, 2012). Ibeanu (2009), observed that between 2003 and early 2005, over 30,000 people died in election related violence in the Niger Delta perpetrated by youths, with properties worth hundreds of millions destroyed. It has equally been noted that over 9000 people have lost their lives in fight between Ijaw gangs (Jawondo, 2011). It is also on record that since 1999, there have been over 90 violent religious conflicts in the country with over 100,000 lives lost in the process (Nwanolue and Iwuoha, 2012).

Religious Conflicts and Education in Nigeria

Education in Nigeria is consisting of three types, namely traditional education, Islamic education and Western education. Traditional education is the type of education practiced in various communities which make up Africa today. This was the system of socialization of individuals into the cherished cultural heritage of the pre-literate society. Fafunwa (1974) asserts that, the aim of traditional education in Africa was to enable the individual learn how to be able to live useful form of life both to himself and the community to which he/she belongs. He stated thus: *“through this indigenous system of education, a child was able to learn the particular type of his/her parent’s profession from the neighbour who was an expert...no parents who engage in a profession, trade or craft would want his/her child to be without an education”*. He would be considered as denying the child the means of livelihood. The traditional system of education was centered round a philosophy that was indigenous. This was the philosophy of functionalism or the philosophy of pragmatism as it is called in the modern time. It was the philosophy based on doing things practically for the purpose of immediate utility. The traditional system of education had cardinal objects, which were grouped broadly into seven aspects. These include: physical training, development of character, respect for elders, per groups and those in authorities, intellectual training, vocational training, community participation and promotion of cultural heritage. The physical training was the aspect, which aims at the physical fitness or development of the individual. And it was carried out through physical exercises

such as jumping, climbing trees, swimming, and boxing, shooting of bows and arrows and playing of various other games.

The development of character in traditional system of education was meant to train the youths and adults morally, socially, and intellectually. This took place with the help of the parents, peer groups and the entire community members. Islamic education is not indigenous to Nigeria, for Islam originated from Arabia and not in Africa. Though Islam penetrated North Africa quite early in its history, it never lost completely its Arabian character. In Nigeria, it was towards the end of the eleventh century, around 1085 AD. So, from 1804 onwards northern Nigeria saw the multiplication of Koranic schools. The growth was so phenomenal that by 1900 AD. Lord Frederick Lugard counted about 20,000 Koranic schools, with a total enrolment of approximately 250,000 pupils. By 1961 AD the figures stood at 27,600 Koranic school with about 423,000 pupils on the roll (Worsely, 1975). By assessment one could say that, except for the moral lessons they were meant to impart, Islamic education as exemplified by the Koranic schools in Nigeria has contributed only marginally to the development of the persons and communities subjected to it. Eminent Nigerian scholars of Muslim persuasion have had cause to complain about the Islamic system of education. Unlike Christianity which discouraged its Nigerian adherents from active participation in the political and economic life of the nation, Muslims have all along approached these sub-sectors on positive notes. Islam had taught the faithful to see themselves as superior to the infidels and should not be subject to the latter's authority.

This was clear from the policies of the nineteenth-century jihadists who not only fought to convert people but appointed, on conquest men of their inner circles to rule them. Similarly, the adoption of Arabic business, acumen has not only made the upper northern states more economically buoyant but placed them to this day at an advantage over the middle belt zone that is predominantly agrarian (Fadeye, 1993). Although Christianity pre-dated Islam in origin, its arrival in Nigeria was about three centuries after Islam. It is indisputable that the first contact of European Christian missionaries with West Africa dated back AD. 1515. But their effort in planting Christianity was short-lived and fruitless because, as in the case of Islam, its initial acceptance was poor. The Oba of Benin who played host to these first missionaries saw no need for any change in faith, being already the custodian of his people culture. The religious instruction class which started in his palace quickly phased out when apathy and ill-health invalidated the missionaries. The interim period between the sixteenth and nineteenth centuries witnessed the traffic in slaves. It was only in the early part of the nineteenth century when Europe no longer needed slaves as a result of their industrial developments that abolition movement brought back the second batch of missionaries to Africa.

This second arrival of missionaries to Nigeria also gave birth to Western education in the country. Education was used by the various missions as a vehicle for evangelism; so, their initial concept of education for Africans was rudimentary enlightenment just enough to enable the converts read the scriptures and moral instructions. The incipient policy was to teach the Africans in their

vernacular. Majority of the missionary organization were so fanatical about this that they were hypersensitive to secular educations. By 1913 there were barely twenty-five primary schools in the whole of the northern region with a total enrolment of 951 pupils. As the government began to invest in education, Lord Lugard decided to control the quality of education being offered to Nigerians. Religious diversity undoubtedly has taken its toll on education in Nigeria. The Northern States in Nigeria are still educationally disadvantaged.

Religious Conflicts and Security in Nigeria

In the discourse of security in Nigeria, Okorie (2011), Jega (2002), Salawu (2010), Onyishi (2011), Ezeoha (2011), Lewis (2002), have identified several causes of security crisis in Nigeria that pose grave consequences to national development. Chief among them is ethno-religious conflicts that tend to have claim many lives in Nigeria. By „ethnic-religious“ it means a situation in which the relationship between members of one ethnic or religious and another of such group in a multiethnic and multi- religious society is characterized by lack of cordiality, mutual suspicion and fear, and a tendency towards violent confrontation (Salawu, 2010:346). Since independence, Nigeria appears to have been bedeviled with ethno-religious conflicts. Over the past decades of her Nationhood, Nigeria has experienced a palpable intensification of religious polarization, manifest in political mobilization, sectarian social movements, and increasing violence (Lewis 2002). However, the inability of the Nigerian leaders to tackle development challenges, distribute state resources equitably and render good services to the people appear to be one of the causes of ethno-religious violence. Salawu (2010) argued that a major cause of what we now see as ethnic-religious conflicts in Nigeria has to do with the accusation and allegations of neglect, oppression, domination, exploitation, victimization, discrimination, marginalization, nepotism and bigotry.

Aliyu (2004) listed global and regional issues that have threatened the Nigerian economic and religious security to include: fundamentalism, corruption, moral decadence, terrorism, environmental problems, among others. There is tension between the preservation of the nation and the rights and freedom of individuals which need adequate measures to protect the sovereignty of nation. Many believe that such measures will adequately address the issues of the rights and freedom of Nigerian citizens, especially where the rule of laws, strict checks and balances seem to have failed. There cannot be nation security amidst religious crises and adequate education. This is so because sound education is the ingredient of moralization which helps the citizens of any nation in restoring comradeship, peaceful co-existence and unity among the people (Cole-Onifiri, 2002). The absence of peace and harmonious relationship pave wide way for violence of all sorts in the nation. Based on this consideration, there will only be peace and national security in Nigeria, if the history of religious conflicts is carefully examined in order to address the multifarious security challenges that have engulfed our nation in contemporary time. This would not only prepare ground for economic

progress, but fertile land for unity, mutual trust, respect and harmonious relationship among the Nigerian citizenry.

Religious Conflicts and Economic Development in Nigeria

Religious conflict in Nigeria has high direct and indirect cost. There is no gain saying that violent conflict seems to be the pathway to poverty and a major challenge to the development of most countries embroiled in conflicts in Africa. In Nigeria, various violent conflicts the country has experienced are taking a heavy toll on the country's development. Adeyemo, (2006 cited in Saheed, 2012) submits that the insecurity of lives and properties which tends to prevent foreign economic relations to jumpstart the economy is one of the major implications of persistent conflicts in the land. In the same vein, Saheed, (2012) revealed that victims of religious conflicts while taking refuge in refugees camp are cut off from optimal engagement in economic activities. In that condition, they cannot make meaningful contributions to the development of the country. The able-bodies wasted in senseless religious and other types of crises in the country can no longer contribute to the socio-political and economic development of Nigeria. Similarly, properties lost to various conflicts and compensations paid by the various governments cannot be ploughed back to developmental objectives. In fact, a total of N150 billion oil revenue has been deferred and property worth billions of naira destroyed in communal clashes nationwide (Yahaya, 2005).

The government of Delta State in 2003 spent N200 million to maintain soldiers stationed in Warri to maintain peace (Adebanwi, 2004). Indeed, conflicts have led to loss of assets both by victims and the diversion of public funds from developments to pay compensation to victims. For example, it is estimated that assets worth fifty-nine million, six hundred and seventy-two thousand Naira (₦59,672,000) were lost to the Jos crisis in 2001, while government compensation to victims was about thirteen million, nine hundred and thirty-eight thousand Naira (₦13,938,000); assets lost to the Kaduna crisis of 2001 amounted to fifty million, six hundred and twenty-five thousand Naira (₦50,625,000), with government compensation at thirty-two million, seven hundred and sixteen thousand Naira (₦32,716,000). The Kano crisis of 2001 resulted in the loss of asset worth fifty-nine million, seven hundred and fifty-six thousand Naira (₦59,756,000), while compensation totaling about twenty-two million, six hundred and fifty-eight thousand Naira (₦22,658,000); assets lost to Jos crisis of 2004 was estimated at about one hundred and two million, nine hundred and thirty-two thousand Naira (₦102,932,000) while eighty five million, one hundred and twenty-one thousand Naira (₦85,121,000) was paid as compensation to victims (to mention just a few) (Yahaya, 2005). Added to the above is the fact that continued insecurity in the country has not only discouraged transnational corporations to invest, but has equally caused the established ones to divest by way of folding up their businesses (Afegbua, 2010).

Religious Conflicts and Migration in Nigeria

The history of the human race is that of migration and conflicts. Man, by nature, is designed to be mobile. He moves, as the need arises, from one location to another in search of a variety of things. In the same vein, conflict is inherent in human relationship. Whether at the interpersonal or organizational/societal or national or international level, human interactions are laced with issues for conflicts. In Africa, like other continents of the world, migration and conflicts have contributed to the making and shaping of the histories of the people. This is because at different points in the political and social histories of the African people, records revealed a large scale of in and out-migration as well as different kinds of conflicts. In recent times, Nigeria has witnessed many protracted and gruesome religious conflicts that have sparked off a wave of demographic movement of people both within and outside of the country. Recently Christians who had houses and all their investments in the Northern part of the country are now migrating to the south to come and start life afresh. Migration scholars have agreed as to the determinants of the phenomenon of migration. The determinants, which are used as the basis of theories or models of migration, cut across a wide spectrum of social, economic, ecological and behavioural factors.

While unemployment and search for cheap labor and social and political oppression are examples of economic and social factors respectively, droughts and desertification and individual attributes and motivations are examples of environmental and behavioural factors of migration respectively. One common fact deducible in both migration and conflict literature is the wholesome agreement on the interrelatedness of the two phenomena. It is a fact in the literature that migration can engender conflicts and vice versa.

Religious Conflicts: Implications for Information Dissemination

Echezona (2007) has extensively discussed the role of libraries in information dissemination for conflict resolution, peace promotion and reconciliation. In her paper, she asserts that recent studies on Information Flow and Sharing have noted that lack of adequate or balanced information was the most significant cause of most of violent conflicts. This seems to be true because, without knowledge and information, there is likely to be a conflict. The African continent witnessed the introduction of “genocide” in the African lexicon in Rwanda in 1994, and evidence points to the negative role of the mass media, especially Radio Miles Colines, in preparing the minds of Hutus against Tutsis. As the apparatus of the Hutu State, the radio station tried to portray Tutsis as demons that must be exterminated from the face of the earth, and in an attempt to wipe the Tutsis out, Hutus themselves suffered one of the worst refugee crises on the African continent (Nnaji, 2001).

Information dissemination can be described as a need comparable with other basic human needs. Free flow of information is a right of the people which enables them to participate effectively in the process of economic, social and political activities in the society, and enhances education, knowledge and learning (Laloo, 2002). Therefore, for any nation to make meaningful impact in conflict

prevention, peace promotion and conflict resolution, early warning information is needed. Timely alert to potential conflicts is central to an early warning system which, in order to be meaningful, must be complemented by early political action. Such alertness underlines the predictive capability of any early warning system. To that extent, therefore, early warning should not be seen as an end in itself, but rather, as a tool for preparedness, prevention and mitigation of conflicts, the efficiency of which is predicated upon a clear methodology for data collection, analysis and information exchange (Ibok and Nhara, quoted in Yaqub, 2001).

Early warning information should be facts on the matter. Some of this early warning information, which could include internet, community radio, television, video conferencing and voice-over of Internet protocol (VoIP), email, print media, and reference services, are important, in order for people to know the implications of embarking on the conflict. This information can be given first to those who can take constructive action. Information literacy is the ability to develop skills, in order to access, decode and use information. Such skills are essential in a growing and complex information society. Literacy in the information society also requires new mental and operational capabilities, enable a person to deal successfully with a highly fluid, evasive and yet strongly structured environment. Information literacy or lack of it is perhaps the most crucial facet of the so-called digital divide (Queau, 2001). The American Library Association defines it as a term “applied to the skills of information problem-solving, and adds that an information-literate person “must be able to recognize when information is needed and have the ability to locate, evaluate, and use effectively the needed information” (American Library Association, 1996), Hawkins (2002), notes that knowledge and information have become the most important currency for productivity, competitiveness, and increased wealth and prosperity. According to Akintunde (2004), ICT “emphasizes the use of the computer and other technologies such as telephone to process, transport, and transfer voice and other data singularly or mixed with least interference or distortion of content.” With the above definition, ICT can be used to either propagate or resolve conflict. For instance, the Nazis had made immense use of the mass media in the Second World War to mobilize the German people (Nnaji, 2001).

Libraries are strategic in conflict resolution. Libraries and librarians have played a major role in creating, accumulating, organizing, and disseminating information. Libraries are key players in fostering the information society. The advance in the area of computer hardware and software, as well as breakthroughs in the field of communications, brought about a great revolution in the way libraries deliver their information service today. With this revolution of ICT systems such as internet, website, email, teleconferencing, and information super high way, etc., libraries can then play a role in conflict resolution. Libraries can have a web site on conflict resolution to reach potential users, NGO and Government. Internet-based services are a more recent introduction, but already, demands for the services are expanding quickly. Library can do that through the creation of a website, where adequate information on conflict resolution can be discussed, accessed and disseminated to a wider

population through email, list serve and teleconferencing. Such information dissemination is needed, in order to succeed with any meaningful conflict resolution or reconciliation. Eytayo (2005) noted that the advent of ICT has provided a bridge for virtual library patrons, who may be in the comfort of their offices or rooms and in dire need of answers to their questions. In order to remain relevant to this new environment, the library needs to pursue with all vigour the provision of online reference services.

This type of service has been referred to as “chat”, “digital”, “email”, “online”, or “virtual” referencing service. Library and information services are key actors in providing unhindered access to essential information resources for economic and cultural advancement. In doing so, they contribute effectively to the development and maintenance of intellectual freedom, democratic values, peace and universal civil right (IFLA, 2002). Libraries can clearly play a major role in conflict resolution in the following ways: Seminar Ogunkelu (2001) stated that seminars would go a long way in equipping researchers in the techniques of identifying and preventing conflicts at their early stages, as well as manage and resolve them. The library could invite experts on conflict resolution as resource persons and provide them with information materials to back up their discussions. The transcripts of the discussions could be put into pamphlets or on tapes. Reports have shown that countries like Ethiopia, Namibia, Uganda, Somalia and Liberia have mobilised library community resources in innovative ways to prevent and resolve conflicts (World Bank, 1996), cited in World Bank (2005). Libraries could also organise seminars not only for the purpose of building the capacity of conflict researchers, but also for informing members of the public on the importance of peace for meaningful development. Extension Services and Indigenous Knowledge Systems Libraries increase the value of human intellectual outputs by enhancing access to them through professional information processing, storage and dissemination functions. Public libraries have a solid tradition of outreach. This outreach means taking the library to the people (mobile libraries), so that they would read to illiterates in their communities, translate, interpret, photocopy, ask, and answer questions concerning human rights.

Conclusion

Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present, without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Religious conflicts have been identified as major constraints to election processes, governance, security, education, migration and economic development. This discourse has brought to the fore that intentional, timely, relevant, authoritative and purposeful information targeted at specific groups and situations can strengthen the human, social, economic and environmental pillars of sustainable development. It is recommended that the application of the CRAAP test to packaging information for religious conflicts would mitigate the escalation of situations. C- Currency: How current is the information, R- Relevance: How related is it to the situation in question, A- Authority: What is the expertise of the author? A- Accuracy: How authentic is the information? P- Purpose: What is the lesson to imbibe? This paper posits that the

positive roles of religion can be intentionally packaged and disseminated to mitigate the negative effects of religious conflicts in Nigeria for sustainable development.

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